

Deliverable D7.1 Report of use-cases and architecture for the EGA federation

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
2. Contribution toward project objectives	2
3. Introduction	4
4. Description of work accomplished	5
4.1 Survey of Use Cases for EGA Federation	5
4.2 Initial Use Case Survey Responses	5
5. Results	7
5.1 Governance	7
5.2 Node Policies and GDPR	9
5.3 Data Management and Standards	10
5.4 Production Services	12
5.5 Technical Infrastructure	13
5.6 Operations Support	15
5.7 Communications, Community Building, and Engagement	16
6. Conclusions	17
7. Impact	17
8. Next Steps	17
9. Deviation from Description of Action	18
10. Appendices	19
Appendix 1: Survey of Use Case for EGA Federation	19

1. Executive Summary

The COVID-19 pandemic has amplified the need for rapid international discovery, access, and sharing of human host genetic and phenotype data, which can be met by accelerating the formation, development, governance, and deployment of the Federated EGA. Here, we collaborated with engaged potential national nodes to establish the needs and national use-cases the nodes intend to address by becoming a part of the Federated EGA network. To achieve this goal, we created a survey (Appendix 1) to gather direct feedback on national use cases for supporting a Federated EGA network. The use case survey was announced at ELIXIR Federated Human Data meetings and

Federated EGA Committee meetings, and shared directly with the first 12 interested nodes, 3 of which completed the survey in time for this report (Table 1). New interested nodes will be provided the survey, and responses from additional surveys will be incorporated as they are completed. Survey responses were analysed for common themes and organized into broader categories to share with other WP7 partners and Federated EGA Committee members. The surveys highlighted a largely overlapping set of use cases and requirements that were organised into “themes” including: regulatory themes (“Governance”, “Node Policies and GDPR”), technical themes, (“Data Management and Standards”, “Technical Infrastructure”, “Production Services”), and support themes (“Operations Support”, “Communications, Community Building, and Engagement”). Each theme includes specific use cases which can be supported by a Federated EGA network through: forming permanent committees and ad hoc working groups, encouraging the use of global and community standards, establishing guidelines for what data/metadata can and cannot be shared within the network, and coordinating on shared approaches and strategies. The results outlined here are key to informing all aspects of establishing the Federated EGA and will directly contribute to technical implementation plans (developed as part of Task 7.2), the minimal FEGA metadata model (developed as part of Task 7.3), and the Federated EGA Node Maturity Model (developed as part of Task 7.4).

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No

Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No

Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No
Objectives - WP7 - Federated European Genome-phenome Archives for transnational access of COVID-19 host data.	
O7.1: Federation architecture, interfaces, and compliance tests for the Federated EGA network (Task 7.1).	Yes
O7.2: Coordination of the development of a reference implementation sufficient to create a functional Federated EGA node (Task 7.2).	Yes
O7.3: Development of phenotype metadata model to enable mapping and linkage of COVID-19 host-clinical measures across European national nodes, and robust linkage between host and viral datasets (Task 7.3).	Yes
O7.4: The development of documentation and guidelines for the operational practices of federated EGA nodes (Task 7.4).	Yes

3. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has amplified the need for rapid international discovery, access, and sharing of human host genetic and phenotype data in order to inform genetic association studies on host susceptibility and severity of disease. CONVERGE WP7 seeks to accelerate the formation, development, governance, and deployment of the Federated EGA as a platform for international discovery and access to human host genetic and phenotypic data. By collaborating with a set of engaged potential national nodes, CONVERGE WP7 aims to establish the governance, architecture and implementations, node maturity model, and coordination of metadata standards. A key first step to engaging with potential nodes is to establish the needs and national use-cases the nodes intend to address through the Federated EGA.

Deliverable scope: This deliverable describes the results of a Federated EGA use case survey that has been distributed to the first set of potential nodes. The goal of the survey was to establish the national use cases and needs that the nodes intend to address, so that we can identify commonalities and ensure that the use cases are addressed by the proposed technical architecture and its corresponding implementation (Task 7.2). This deliverable is satisfied by getting feedback on use cases from the first Federated EGA nodes that have started work to become operational or are Task 7.1 Partners, namely: Finland - CSC/ELIXIR-FI, Sweden - UU/ELIXIR-SE, Portugal - FCG-IGC and INESC-ID/ELIXIR-PT, and Spain - CRG and BSC/ELIXIR-ES. Input will be reviewed and incorporated

from additional interested groups as they provide feedback and use cases. More technical details of the network architecture are in scope for Task 7.2.

Relationship with other WPs: This output of this deliverable will inform the development of the Federated EGA maturity model, which is a joint collaboration between Task 7.4 and WP5 through the development of the prioritised demonstrator: 'Federated access to human genomics data'.

Methodology: We created a survey (Appendix 1, one survey shared with each Federated node) to gather direct feedback on use cases for supporting a Federated EGA network. Survey responses were reviewed for common themes, organized into broader categories, and aggregated into a report to share with other WP7 groups and Federated EGA Committees.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Survey of Use Cases for EGA Federation

To gather feedback from groups who are interested in joining FEGA, we created a use case survey (Appendix 1: "Use Case for EGA Federation¹") to collect feedback from interested FEGA nodes. The survey asks open-ended questions on topics including: "Project and initiative goals", "Solutions for meeting goals", "Measures of success", "Personal Data and Federated EGA". These topics were chosen to focus on understanding high-level use cases and future goals of EGA Federation which are likely largely shared among nodes. It was important to include a question about how nodes envision personal data will be managed within the Federation as this is one of the key drivers for establishing the Federation. Questions about implementation details were intentionally avoided because implementation choices will depend not only on use cases but also on other restrictions such as funding, existing technical expertise, and national regulations.

Potential Federated EGA nodes were asked to complete the survey so results could be aggregated and discussed in collaboration with other WP7 task groups and the Federated EGA committee to inform how the proposed governance, organisational, and technical designs will address the national use cases.

4.2 Initial Use Case Survey Responses

The use case survey was announced at ELIXIR FHD meetings and FEGA committee meetings. Surveys (shared Google documents) were individually created for and shared with potential FEGA nodes to collect their input on the various topics. Surveys were directly shared with representatives from the

¹https://docs.google.com/document/d/1lg0rVUI63Y9zcNA4ikVIVx6TCAdev_n8JPsh7_F4d-M/edit?usp=sharing

first five Federated EGA nodes (Finland, Germany, Norway, Spain, and Sweden) as well as subsequent groups that expressed interest in joining FEAGA (Luxembourg, Netherlands, Portugal, Greece, Slovenia).

Table 1: Status of use case surveys shared with interested Federated EGA nodes.

Node (organisation)	Node membership status	Use case survey status
Finland (CSC/ELIXIR-FI)	In progress	Done
Germany (DKFZ, Uni-Tübingen, EMBL/GHGA/ELIXIR-DE)	In progress	Done
Luxembourg (UNILU/ELIXIR-LU)	Interested	Done
Netherlands (DTL/ELIXIR-NL)	Interested	In progress
Portugal (FCG-IGC, INESC-ID/ELIXIR-PT)	Interested	In progress
Spain (CRG,BSC/ELIXIR-ES)	In progress	Invited
Norway (UIO/ELIXIR-NO)	In progress	Invited
Sweden (UU/ELIXIR-SE)	In progress	Invited
Greece (BSRC/ELIXIR-GR)	Interested	Invited
Slovenia (UL MF/ELIXIR-SI)	Interested	Invited

The ELIXIR Federated Human Data community consists of 18 ELIXIR nodes that are in various stages of engagement and planning with their national funders to establish a Federated EGA node. We will continue to solicit responses to the use case survey at ELIXIR FHD meetings and other FEAGA meetings. New survey responses will be periodically assessed to identify new, emerging use cases and how they will be supported by FEAGA.

After receiving the first three survey responses, the responses were analysed to identify common use cases, divergent use cases, concerns, and expectations. These topics were then grouped into a set of “themes” for supporting the Federated EGA network. The themes were also organised in a way that they could form a framework for organisations to consider what is required for establishing a Federated EGA node, potentially feeding into the maturity model (Task 7.4) and technical implementations (Task 7.2).

5. Results

Based on the feedback obtained from the Federated EGA Use Case Surveys, use case themes were identified. The themes are roughly ordered from more strategic to more operational.

1. Governance
2. Node Policies and GDPR
3. Data Management and Standards
4. Technical Infrastructure
5. Production Services
6. Operations Support
7. Communications, Community Building, and Engagement

Each theme is discussed with examples pulled directly from submitted surveys. Descriptions of the theme use cases are provided along with how the Federated EGA network will support the use cases.

5.1 Governance

The EGA project was initially established at EMBL-EBI in 2008, and became a co-managed resource with CRG from 2012, governed by agreements between the two institutions. As EGA expands to include additional partners and types of nodes, the governance structures need to evolve to support a federated network of partners with additional use-cases and priorities. The Federated EGA will consist of a diverse set of national nodes tasked with archiving, hosting, and sharing human biomolecular data in a manner that is consistent with their national regulations and serves their national use-cases. Therefore, it is vital to understand the use cases for addressing governance strategy, vision, and sustainability of these national nodes.

5.1.1 Governance strategy

All nodes indicated a strong desire to establish close collaborations and cooperation among all members of the Federated EGA network with regard to overall strategy and governance. Luxembourg, for example, stated that a successful relationship between Central EGA and their Federated EGA node would include *“joint discussion and decision (with clear procedure) on strategy and development... More or less the relationship between ELIXIR nodes: parallel partner, between-nodes collaborations on common interests and exchange of technologies and ideas.”* Finland agreed, stating that *“nodes need to be part of the planning process, with Central EGA, to obtain a distributed knowledge about the customer actions and documentation.”*

Despite this general agreement, some questions remain with regard to how the Federated network will be governed, the long-term plans and roadmap for Federated EGA, and future collaborations. There are also ongoing discussions regarding the legal agreements that must be signed between

Central EGA and Federated EGA nodes to ensure that they are acceptable by all parties wanting to join the federation. Input from the survey results and subsequent discussions with the likely inaugural nodes (Finland, Germany, Norway, Spain, and Sweden) is informing establishment of the Federated EGA Committees and Working Group structures, which are expected to be finalised and become operational by end of Q2 2021.

5.1.2 Vision and goals

Given the anticipated heterogeneity of nodes within the Federated network, it is imperative that the Federated EGA shares a common vision and set of core principles. In Q1 2021 we co-drafted with the inaugural five nodes a shared vision statement for the Federated EGA:

The Federated EGA strives to support the discovery of and secure access to human data globally, while respecting national data protection regulations, with the goal of accelerating disease research and understanding and improving human health.

Vision and goals of individual Federated EGA nodes, while generally aligned with the FEGA vision statement, are distinct and reflect broad use cases for establishing nodes. It will be important for Federated nodes to establish their visions and goals early on to help define their scope and specific requirements. A few example node visions are noted here:

“CSC’s goal is to promote data interoperability and allow Finnish human consented data sharing across borders in compliance with local and international standards (e.g. GDPR). In this manner, we want to support European research and foster reuse of human research data.” - Finland

“A platform that covers (dynamics and federated) data discovery, access request/approval management, central access information service (to other softwares/applications), download, visualization, well-tested processing pipeline and (federated) analysis.” - Luxembourg

“The German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA) seeks to establish a national data infrastructure for human (gen)omics data in Germany. ... The ultimate dream, of course, is a seamless data infrastructure enabling the automated, federated analysis of large-scale genomics data as well as associated clinical data across European borders.” - Germany

5.1.3 Sustainability

Sustainability and funding was mentioned by almost all nodes as being essential to ensure that Federated EGA infrastructure has a long lifetime and can continue serving the needs of the research community. In many cases, nodes have recently received national funding for an initial period of a few years. Securing sustainable funding for node infrastructure was mentioned as a challenge for multiple nodes to meet their goals, in some cases directly affecting their overall goals for FEGA. It is clear that

sustainable funding for Federated nodes is a major concern and an area where large-scale, cooperative, and creative approaches would be welcomed.

How “Governance” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by the establishment of committees and working groups to address strategic concerns and clarify open questions about Federated EGA network governance and sustainability. The FEGA Founding Committee - with representation from Central EGA, Federated EGA nodes, and ELIXIR Hub - meets regularly to discuss FEGA governance and strategy. Ad hoc FEGA working groups will be established as needed to address specific tasks. The governance use case is also supported by the EGA legal agreement being signed between Central EGA and each FEGA node.

5.2 Node Policies and GDPR

Until recently, most individual-level human ‘omics’ data has been generated in the context of research consortia. More recently there has been an emergence of large cohort data from humans generated by national or regional healthcare initiatives, which has specifically been accelerated due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Genetic data generated in a healthcare context is subject to more stringent information governance than research data and must adhere to national data regulations and laws. In addition to policies governing the Federated EGA as a whole, policies and legal agreements are required for individual nodes to govern the genetics data they will be responsible for. The details of these policies and agreements will be unique to each node depending on the services they provide and the national regulations to which they are required to adhere. For example, Finland has passed the Secondary use of Health and Social Data Act and the Data Protection Act of Finland, the former mandates how healthcare data can be used for research and the latter is a supplementary implementation act of the GDPR, Finland has additional laws and regulations on the processing of personal data².

5.2.1 Data protection

Nodes indicated a requirement to adhere to national laws and regulations, including GDPR, to promote sharing of sensitive data generated within their local jurisdictions. A few examples are noted here:

“CSC’s goal is to promote data interoperability and allow Finnish human consented data sharing across borders in compliance with local and international standards (e.g. GDPR).” - Finland

“We are fully under the GDPR regulation, any sharing of personal data to other organisations needs to be analyzed.” - Luxembourg

² <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/legislation>

Multiple formal processes exist that can help nodes assess how well they adhere to data protection regulations. A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) can be used to identify and minimise data protection risks. A vulnerability assessment can be used to identify, quantify, and prioritize risks and vulnerabilities. A risk assessment can be used to identify potential threats and the probability that these factors will result in a security breach.

Nodes recognised to different degrees that further work is needed to clarify data protection as well as ethical, legal, and social implications (ELSI) in their individual cases. An ad hoc FEAGA working group consisting of ELSI and Data Protection expertise from the nodes should be established to address this need.

5.2.2 Legal agreements

Nodes want to provide streamlined and intuitive processes for users to submit data, a key part of which is establishing node-specific policies around data transfers and data protection. Examples of these policies include Data Processing Agreements (DPA), Material Transfer Agreements (MTA), Data Transfer Agreements (DTA), and Data Access Agreements (DAAs). Such agreements support GDPR requirements for defining roles (e.g. Data Controller, Data Processor) and responsibilities.

How “Node Policies and GDPR” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by policies defining a federated network where sensitive data and sensitive metadata - including clinical and healthcare information - remain local to Federated nodes, and only public metadata is shared between Federated nodes and Central EGA. For example, Germany indicates they “... *will share technical metadata as well as non-sensitive metadata with Central EGA.*” By restricting sensitive data and sensitive metadata to Federated nodes, they can establish their own legal agreements to adhere to national regulations and support the needs of their users.

5.3 Data Management and Standards

One of the major responsibilities of the Federated EGA network is to ensure that the management of sensitive human data and sensitive metadata adheres to national laws and regulations. It is imperative to provide assurance to researchers that solutions are in place to prevent unauthorised access to sensitive data. Equally important is to ensure that when authorisation is given, data are in fact able to be accessed in a straightforward way and interpreted easily. Through the implementation of technical solutions and standards, these goals can be achieved by all nodes in the Federated EGA network.

5.3.1 Data flow

Nodes agree that a vital aspect of Federated EGA is understanding data and metadata flow within the network. While centralising information at Central EGA is necessary to support data discovery, this process must be balanced with the requirements to keep sensitive data and sensitive metadata local to the Federated nodes. Specifically, Germany indicated that they would consider a successful Federated node one that supports “*being able to accept and validate (local) genomic data and to forward the necessary metadata to the Central EGA*”.

Federated nodes also require the ability to provide data and metadata transfer options for different types of users, ranging from more experienced and resource-rich users to less experienced users. Nodes plans to build both programmatic as well as UI-based tools to support their users. Technical implementations to support data flow processes will likely be unique to each node given local expertises and restrictions, although the use of the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH³) standards like htsget⁴ and Crypt4GH⁵ are encouraged to.

5.3.2 Standards

Federated nodes aim to support a variety of data types that extend beyond genotype and phenotype data. These data types include, but are not limited to: whole genome/exome sequencing, RNA-seq, single-cell RNA-seq and other -omics sequencing, CHIP-seq, targeted sequencing, genotyping, proteomics, microarrays, methylation arrays, metagenomics, and imaging. Nodes also plan to support related data types such as gut microbiome, viral sequencing, electronic health records, histopathological images, CT and MRI scans, and clinical cohort data. Encouraging the use of community standards for these data - e.g. the GA4GH standards CRAM, BAM, and VCF⁶ for genomic data and Phenopackets⁷ for clinical information - would support data interoperability for the research community.

A shared metadata model is another standard necessary for establishing a Federated node. Adopting a shared minimal metadata standard (being developed as part of WP7.3) and the use of standard vocabularies and ontologies would contribute greatly to metadata interoperability, in particular within the Federated EGA network. As Germany describes, “*One of the biggest advantages of the Federated EGA is the centralization of necessary metadata to create a single point of entry for researchers looking for appropriate data to cooperate their research.*”

5.3.3 Data security

³ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

⁴ <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/htsget.html>

⁵ <https://crypt4gh.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶ <https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/>

⁷ <https://phenopackets-schema.readthedocs.io/en/1.0.0/index.html>

Nodes require the ability to manage access to sensitive data and sensitive metadata to prevent unauthorized access. Operationally, this requires the ability to manage user requests for access, communicate with DACs to approve or deny requests, and manage permissions for authorized users. Managing access also requires implementing authentication and authorisation standards, for example GA4GH researcher IDs⁸ as well as secure protocols for accessing or downloading data. For Germany, a successful Federated node is “able to broker access requests, stage archived data, and provide a secure download technology”.

How “Data Management and Standards” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by a federated network that encourages interoperability at multiple levels: API interfaces with clear SOPs for data flow; standard formats for data and metadata; authentication and authorisation standards for managing researcher IDs; and the use of technologies that are agnostic to data types and flexible enough to support emerging experimental techniques.

5.4 Production Services

The EGA currently provides production services for data submission, validation, archive, discovery, and distribution. These services are continuously being improved and additional services are developed in response to user needs. Federated EGA nodes provide a similar set of services to instantiate their node and serve their local users specifically.

5.4.1 Scope

All nodes surveyed so far have identified a range of specific services that they aim to provide for a variety of user groups. In addition to providing core Central EGA services (data archive, data discovery, data access), Federated nodes plan to provide additional services such as unified data processing, bespoke community portals, data visualization, and federated data analysis. Some nodes indicated plans to provide production services for specific research communities, for example rare disease and cancer, in addition to general research groups. Some nodes will focus on services for local users, while others plan to be a platform for global communities or coordinate with existing transnational initiative (e.g. B1MG⁹). Finally, nodes have expressed slightly nuanced focuses on research communities, healthcare initiations, or both. Germany provided one example of their intended scope of services:

“In addition to archiving and cataloguing this data, GHGA will offer additional community features and will in particular curate and uniformly process selected datasets. These extended

⁸ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/tree/master/researcher_ids

⁹ <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

services will be available for selected communities initially, in particular rare disease and cancer, for which we will also operate bespoke community portals.” - Germany

5.4.2 Production service support

To support their respective production services, Federated nodes will require a common set of supporting processes and products including (but not limited to):

- Risk register and vulnerability assessment
- Benchmarking and compliance testing
- Security incident notification process and breach response plan
- Continuous integration and continuous delivery/deployment processes

The development of guidelines for these processes and products can be shared within the Federated EGA network, with individual nodes implementing their own versions based on their needs. Nodes can also implement additional support services as required. These processes and products will also inform the Federated EGA Maturity Model (being developed as part of Task 7.4) to provide a framework for nodes to become operational.

How “Production Services” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by a federated network that enables nodes to develop independently while maintaining support for core services required to be a part of the federation. The FEAGA network can collaborate to establish general guidelines and strategies that nodes can then implement individually.

5.5 Technical Infrastructure

Federated EGA nodes will require technical solutions to both support their own goals and production services, as well as to interact with Central EGA and potentially other nodes within the network. Technical solutions will be diverse, but should adhere to principles that support interoperability and shared community standards.

5.5.1 Node organisation

Nodes need to be able to choose a specific organizational structure that is in line with their government and funding requirements. One option is for a federated node to be represented by one institution in one country, as is the case for Federated EGA Finland hosted at the IT Center for Science (CSC). Another option is for a Federated node to be represented by multiple institutions within the same country, as is the case with Federated EGA Germany (German Human Genome-phenome Archive) co-hosted by German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ), European

Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), and the University of Tübingen. It is also possible that a Federated EGA node is itself federated as multiple smaller “nodes”, where each smaller “node” is a hospital or institution. This model is in discussion by Federated EGA Netherlands and Portugal.

5.5.2 Software stack

All nodes indicated a requirement to be interoperable with Central EGA and other Federated nodes as well as to be able to deploy required software stacks. The choice of software stack for a particular node will depend on node expertise, existing software components, and the service needs of the node. Nodes might also choose to adopt a microservices architecture approach or a monolith, depending on their needs. There is no requirement for all Federated nodes to implement identical software stacks, as long as nodes can interact with each other and with Central EGA via standard APIs.

5.5.3 Infrastructure

Federated nodes require sufficient storage, computing, and network resources to support their services and the ability to integrate with existing local and national infrastructures. Nodes are taking different approaches to establishing their infrastructure, from building new infrastructure from scratch, relying on existing institutional infrastructure, or making use of existing national or transnational infrastructures (e.g. ELIXIR¹⁰, EOSC¹¹). In addition, nodes are relying on local infrastructure (e.g. Norway), cloud-based infrastructure (e.g. Sweden), or a hybrid model (e.g. Finland) depending on their requirements. For example:

“GHGA hosted datasets will also be made available via national cloud infrastructures, thereby allowing users to perform compute intensive analyses without the need to download any data to local compute infrastructures.” - Germany

Regardless of the chosen infrastructure, nodes must implement authentication and authorisation infrastructure to prevent unauthorised access of sensitive data and sensitive metadata. AAI can be supported using both hardware and software components and following community standards, e.g. from GA4GH¹².

How “Technical Infrastructure” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by agreement among the Federated EGA network to use community standards to implement technical solutions. Given the diversity of services planned at individual nodes and organisational or institutional restrictions, a single technical infrastructure will not necessarily be useful for every node in the Federated network. Instead, interfaces between nodes

¹⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

¹² <https://github.com/ga4gh/data-security/blob/master/AAI/AAIConnectProfile.md>

will be governed by community standards and documented APIs to support interoperability. Nodes are then able to establish infrastructures and deploy software stacks that are required to support the services and operations they will provide. For Federated nodes wanting to quickly deploy a software stack, Central EGA offers an open source solution named LocalEGA¹³ which has already been used in the initial technical testing phase of the Federated EGA.

5.6 Operations Support

With policies, production services, and technical infrastructure in place, nodes should be able to become operational. To successfully operate a Federated EGA node, support will be needed for both internal staff and external users.

5.6.1 Standard Operating Procedures & documentation

Federated node operations require SOPs and documentation to ensure a simple, easy to understand, fast, and well-supported user experience. SOPs and documentation are needed for 1) user-facing processes, 2) internal Federated node operations, and 3) interactions between FEAGA nodes and Central EGA. This list of SOPs/documents includes, but is not limited to: Helpdesk SOPs, documentation and FAQs for data submitters and data requestors, documentation and FAQs for analysis platforms/services, internal guidelines for managing FEAGA node software and infrastructure, SOPs for raising operational concerns within the Federated EGA network.

5.6.2 Staff training

All nodes indicated a need to develop guidelines for both staff training to operate the node and for providing support for users. At Central EGA, the Helpdesk is a key component of training and will be important for Federated nodes, as well. Nodes indicated a desire to share common aspects of staff and user training in order to provide a unified experience for all Federated EGA network users. This could include, for example, training on principles and guidelines for managing controlled access data within the Federated EGA network. Some training will need to be bespoke for the particular infrastructure and operations of a node.

How “Operations Support” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by a Federated EGA network that identifies shared or common operational areas where central and Federated nodes can collaborate to develop operational support materials (e.g. Helpdesks). Key points of contact at each node could form working groups to share operational concerns and investigate solutions together. The already established FEAGA Operations Committee will oversee FEAGA network operations, and the FEAGA maturity model (Task 7.4) will

¹³ <https://localega.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

provide an on-boarding guide to prospective nodes from initial planning through becoming a fully operational node.

5.7 Communications, Community Building, and Engagement

Federated EGA does not exist without scientific communities contributing data to and using data from the resource in support of research goals and healthcare initiatives. A large and often underappreciated aspect of providing a research service is proactively building and engaging with the user communities, which is necessary to ensure the service is fit for purpose.

5.7.1 Strategy

All nodes want to join and contribute to a growing community of services enabling transnational access to and federated analysis of large-scale genomics and clinical data. Nodes agreed that one of the major benefits of joining Federated EGA is being able to join an existing community of experts dedicated to promoting discovery and access of genetic and phenotypic data. *“Joining a federated network promotes also exchange of professional competences (for example in data archiving and stewardship, software development, training solutions), data and solutions interoperability and encourages coordination efforts.”* (Finland). It is important to nodes to continue this theme of community building and engagement as the federation develops.

Nodes agreed that clarifying a communications strategy is key to engaging with local and global communities. They expressed interest in formalising communication and branding plans to ensure unified messaging.

How “Communications, Community Building, and Engagement” use cases are met by the proposed Federated EGA network. The use cases described above are supported by a Federated EGA network that, from the beginning, incorporates communications and community building/engagement strategies. These strategies will require building upon existing institutional expertise in reaching local user communities as well as close collaboration among members of the Federated network to present an unified Federated EGA message. An ad hoc FEAGA working group can be established as needed to address specific tasks, and collaboration with CONVERGE WP2¹⁴ (Training and Capacity Building) will also be useful for engaging FEAGA community members.

6. Conclusions

¹⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge/wp2>

With the surveys completed so far, the use cases and requirements of a first wave of national nodes have been identified. The surveys identified the individual node visions and plans, and it is reassuring that the responses were largely overlapping and pointed at a shared set of “themes”. The responses were organised into regulatory themes (“Governance”, “Node Policies and GDPR”), technical themes, (“Data Management and Standards”, “Technical Infrastructure”, “Production Services”), and support themes (“Operations Support”, “Communications, Community Building, and Engagement”), each with specific use cases. The themes will be useful to help define the FEGA Maturity Model (T7.4) and will also be considered in tandem with the technical implementation required for a Federated EGA network (T7.2).

The survey results enabled us to map how the Federated EGA network could support the specific use cases. Support includes forming permanent committees and ad hoc working groups, encouraging the use of global and community standards (e.g. technical standards, data standards), establishing guidelines for what data/metadata can and cannot be shared within the network, and coordinating on shared approaches (e.g. Helpdesk, communications strategy). Further technical implementation details are being developed as part of Task 7.2, and further details on a shared FEGA metadata model are being developed as part of Task 7.3.

7. Impact

The results of the Use Case Surveys are key to informing all aspects of establishing the Federated EGA including governance and legal considerations, establishment of the Federated EGA network technical architecture and standards, node operations, and user engagement. The results obtained so far have been shared with other WP7 task leads and will be valuable reference material for future work. To date, three nodes have completed the survey (Finland, Germany, Luxembourg), two nodes are currently working on the survey (Netherlands, Portugal), and an additional five nodes have been invited to complete the survey (Greece, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Slovenia).

8. Next Steps

The use cases survey will continue to be shared with additional nodes in the ELIXIR FHD community to capture national use cases. New survey responses will be shared as they are completed. Specifically, survey results will be used to help inform in more detail the technical implementations and standards required for a Federated EGA network (T7.2). Ad hoc working groups will be established to address specific technical implementation needs, for example to finalise the API interfaces and the set of compliance tests needed for a node to join the network. Additionally, survey results will help inform the development of the Federated EGA Maturity Model and what is needed for a Federated EGA node to become operational (T7.4). The Maturity Model is likely to evolve as new surveys are completed and new use cases identified. Ad hoc working groups will be established

to address specific operational tasks, for example to establish guidelines for running individual Federated EGA node Helpdesks. Use cases will also continue to drive discussions of the Federated EGA Founding and Operations Committees.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

10. Appendices

Appendix 1: Survey of Use Case for EGA Federation

As part of ELIXIR CONVERGE WP7.1 regarding use-cases and architecture for EGA federation, we are coordinating the documenting of use cases for Federated EGA. As one of the first groups working towards setting up a Federated EGA node, your input to this discussion is key. We kindly request that you or someone you delegate to complete the following survey by <date>. We will incorporate your responses into a single report and circulate for final comments before the deliverable deadline. Thank you in advance for your contributions!

Project and initiative goals

To understand your goals and how they align with Federated EGA, please answer the following questions.

1. What are your “big picture” goals for archiving and providing access to the deposited controlled access human data?
2. What is the timeline for these goals?
3. What types of controlled access human data are you working with, e.g. genomic (WGS, WES, targeted sequencing), genotypic, proteomic?
4. What other types of data are you working with that complement the controlled access human data (e.g. EHR, viral sequencing) but will be archived somewhere else?
5. What challenges or restrictions (e.g. technical, legislative, management) do you currently face or anticipate facing in the future for meeting your goals?

Solutions for meeting goals

To understand how Federated EGA supports your project goals, please answer the following questions.

1. Other than Federated EGA, what options have you considered to meet your goals?
2. How do the current Federated EGA proposals meet your goals? (*e.g. what benefits does FEAGA have over other options? What challenges, barriers, or restrictions are overcome by FEAGA?*)
3. How do the current Federated EGA proposals not meet your needs?
4. What needs are you not sure if or how Federated EGA could meet?

Measures of success

To understand what a successful Federated EGA node means to you, please answer the following questions.

1. What does a successful Federated EGA node look like for your organisation or institute, and what aspects of Federated EGA align with your definition of success?
2. Who are your different types of users and what would a satisfied user experience with your Federated EGA node look like for them?
3. What does a successful relationship between Central EGA and your Federated EGA node look like to you or your users? (*e.g. modes of communication, software updates, strategic planning*)
4. What does a successful relationship between your Federated EGA node and other Federated EGA nodes look like to you and your users?
5. What training and documentation is required for successful operation of your Federated EGA node? (*e.g. training for staff or users, documentation translated into local languages*)
6. What branding or outreach is required for your Federated EGA node - in contrast to Central EGA branding - in order to support your intended users?

Personal Data and Federated EGA

Personal data in Federated EGA covers any identifiable information received by the nodes, including:

- Submitters - names, addresses, and contact information
- Requesters - names, addresses, and contact information
- DACs - names, addresses, and contact information
- Study participants - genetic data, and identifiable phenotypic information

Most nodes are expected to be subject to GDPR and potentially additional national regulations. We expect nodes will have access to data protection (DP) expertise in order to put appropriate DP measures in place for their node to operate, possibly drawing on DP experience and knowledge from Central EGA or other established FEAGA nodes.

We would like to understand how you envision personal data being shared between your Federated EGA node and Central EGA (*e.g. data permissions, contact information, private metadata*). Thinking about how your node will operate, please provide your thoughts on the use cases or needs for personal data to be shared between your Federated EGA node and Central EGA.

Anything else

If there is anything else about your use case for Federated EGA that you'd like to share, please include it here.

Thank you!

